

ADVANCING HEALTH RESEARCH THROUGH DATA SHARING

As part of the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) Health Studies Australian National Data Asset (HeSANDA) Program we are pleased to present this national research symposium.

Wednesday 25 October
10:30am-12:30pm (AEDT)
10:00am-12:00noon (ACDT)

Registration

ONLINE VIA WEBINAR

IN PERSON
Shangri La, Sydney

(hosted at ALLG ASM)

Who should attend?

Researchers, data custodians, clinical trialists, and anyone interested in how to maximise the potential of health research data.

TOPIC	SPEAKER
Beyond Open Data: Embracing FAIR Data Sharing Principles	Matthias Liffers, ARDC
Case Study: Shared Benefits in Research (provider & user perspectives)	Prof Alison Yung, Deakin University
Unlocking Data for Secondary Research: Impacts on Future Research & Health Outcomes	Prof Douglas Boyle, University of Melbourne
Health Data Australia Showcase	Rhys Williams, ARDC
Your Data Sharing Questions Answered	Panel discussion with representatives from ARDC, ANZCTR, University of Melbourne and Deakin University

This event is presented by project 'node' teams from across Australia's [HeSANDA network](#):

- South Australian Node (Administered by SAHMRI)
- National Cancer Cooperative Trials Group Node (Administered by Australian Leukaemia and Lymphoma Group)
- Mental Health Node (Administered by Deakin University)
- Melbourne Academic Centre for Health (MACH) Clinical Trials Consortium Node (Administered by The University of Melbourne)

With acknowledgement to

